

JOURNAL OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES AND INNOVATIVE RESEARCH (JETIR)

An International Scholarly Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal

PODCASTING AS A TOOL FOR IMPROVING ACCENT IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Chaabane Dorsaf

Msc masters- English Language Teacher

Higher Institute of Languages of Nabeul- University of Carthage

ABSTRACT

As technological development keeps surging, language learning became a more attractive experience. However, many English language learners complain about the inability to acquire a good accent despite technological advancement, leading to a lack of self confidence, self esteem and frustration with the process of accent acquisition. In this context, there is a limited research investigating the effectiveness of new technology in acquiring the desired accent. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the correlation between technological tools and accent improvement. This article questions whether the use of podcasts can be a beneficial tool for improving accent in undergraduate English language students in a Tunisian context. As a class project, students were allowed to create their own 5 minutes podcasts in the English language. Mixed research surveys were conducted later to assess the experience. Data analysis proved that the podcast experience was perceived positively by students, and they enjoyed the opportunity of language use and accent improvement. However, there were some challenges, notably, cybersecurity, time and technological access. Main findings show how podcasts enhance accent improvement through focused listening and rehearsal. Thus, integrating podcasts into language learning significantly improved students' pronunciation and accent and had positive impact on their autonomy, engagement and motivation and character.

Key words : language learning, accent, podcasts.

INTRODUCTION

It is a fact, now, that many educational institutions worldwide Embraced the United nations sustainable development goals (SDGs), showing the willingness to adopt a quality education, that is, fosterig a more“inclusive” or “sustainable” education (SDG4) or making students aware of ecological damage and motivating them to better protect the environment through responsible consumption (SDG 12). Hence, teaching for sustainability gave birth to new alternative education means that emphasize planetary protection. Kopnina, H. (2020).

In the same stream, many universities have urged their institutions to become paper free. This entails the reliance on platforms such as ‘google classroom’ for downloading course contents. Students rely on technological tools to study namely personal mobile smartphones. Consequently, Language teachers had to undertake the challenge and find ways to adapt their curriculum to the dramatic shift and create more engaging, effective and sustainable activities.

This over dependence on technology can have some side effects. In fact, old school methods are no more attractive for students. In addition, there is the illusion of knowledge because of the abundance, ubiquity and easy access to information through the availability of internet, which makes the mission of educators harder to accomplish.

Nowadays, according to Tutku başöz (2016) « It is claimed that social media has an enormous role for a high quality education corresponding to the social settings of learning and fostering critical thinking in students (Mason, 2006). There are even researchers suggesting that it has potential to change educational system completely, encouraging students for superior learning instead of being inactive participants of a classroom (Ziegler, 2007). »

In fact, face-to-face communication is withdrawing and giving the floor to social media in contemporary world. However, it is important to remind ourselves that voice makes up to 38% of non-verbal communication according to the Mehrabian '3 V' rule. Indeed, a pivotal part of podcasts is voice.

Thus, the use of podcasts in an audio or video form can enhance autonomous language learning, motivation, creativity and critical thinking.

Which technological tools ?

Call = computer assisted language learning

Mall=mobile assisted language learning

AI= artificial intelligence

Limitations of these technological tools :

The integration of computer technology CALL in language classrooms can be highly beneficial « if both teachers and students possess adequate knowledge and proficiency in the necessary software programs. » Sehan, Z. (2024)

In terms of MALL, Grönlund, Å. (2012) found that « most of the reviewed studies were experimental, small-scale, and conducted within a short period of time. There was also a lack of cumulative research. » Grönlund, Å. (2012)

Concerning the use of AI, Warschauer, M, & Xu, Y. (2024) confirmed that when students engaged with AI, chatbots interactions were more transactional compared to interactions with a human partner which were more relational.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Alternative education in accordance with Sustainable development goals (SDGs)

In accordance with sustainable education, there is a growing need for innovative methods in teaching. The inclusion of podcasts in the learning experience is a winning topic notably with the surge of social media platforms and ubiquitous use of smartphones.

According to Charif, Ben-boulaid (2013) « the combination of mobile technologies and education can create a new instructional method called "edutainment." This approach merges entertainment with learning, making the educational process more engaging and effective, support was motivated by increasing number of mobile users who became attracted to phone-based programs such as smartphones and tablets applications around the world(ally et al.2005). » Charif, Ben-boulaid (2013)

Over the years numerous researchers have documented the efficacy of technological use in language learning mainly speaking and communication.

Limitations of AI and CALL tools

Despite the progress, many studies were conservative about the efficacy of chatbots, highlighting the fact that they are not relational Warschauer, M, & Xu, Y. (2024). There is much uncertainty about the efficacy of these technological tools.

Kilickaya, F. (2006) States that «Today, we have access to many CALL programs that are currently used and tested in language classrooms for teaching grammar, speaking and other skills. Text-to-speech technology is a common feature of almost any CALL application. 'Text-to-Speech' (Speech Synthesis) technology is the ability of a computer to produce 'spoken words'. Limitations are that there is always a difference in terms of intonation and stress. In other words, it still lacks the complexity of naturally occurring speech, resulting in 'dead' sound having no emotions. » Kilickaya, F. (2006).

Podcasts for listening

There is considerable research about the use of podcasts as a tool to enhance listening skills. For example, Indahsari, D. (2020) found that as digital recordings, podcasts can be used to enhance English language learning, mainly the listening skill.

Podcasts for speaking

Nevertheless only few studies have investigated the possibility of using podcasts for accent improvement. As Gulbarshyn, et all (2024) found that podcasts integration into language learning improved students' communicative competence to a significant level, and had « positive correlation with engagement, and curated vocabulary and phrases. » Gulbarshyn, et all (2024)

Findings of Sven L., et al. (2019) highlight the importance of vocal practice and overt repetition as a beneficial method for improving pronunciation. Not to mention that, we can compare repetition to rehearsal, in our research, as students had to repeat their voice recordings several times before reaching the desired outcome.

Leticia, et al. (2018), confirms that dramatisation researchers, use real materials such as podcasts or vodcasts in TEFL and highlight the multiple benefits of these tools in « every communicative skill, autonomous learning and the development of their motivation and interest on the language and culture of English speaking countries. » Leticia, et al. (2018)

Ducate, L. and Lomicka, L. (2009) confirmed that podcasting could be used for honing pronunciation skills in intermediate language learning. « Students appreciated the feedback given for each scripted recording and enjoyed opportunities for creativity during the extemporaneous podcasts. Future studies might seek to delineate more specific guidelines or examine how teacher involvement might be adapted to the use of podcasts as a companion to classroom instruction. » Ducate, L. and Lomicka, L. (2009)

Phillips, Birgit (2017) proved that “Student podcasting assignments show great promise for fostering language production skills due to the high-level cognitive processes involved in producing podcasts”

Hence this study aims to create innovative teaching techniques for language learners in a digital context which is using podcasts as a tool to improve accent, autonomy, motivation, and self efficacy, BAŞARAN (2014).

METHODOLOGY

Secondary data analysis was conducted for research. External data was collected to assess the impact of mobile phone use on youth, likewise, the impact of social media on daily schedule.

As a class project, students were allowed to create their own podcasts on a topic of choice in the English language. The length of each podcast is five minutes in average. The podcasts were made by first year undergraduate English language students in the university of Carthage in Tunisia, the subject was soft skills.

Surveys were conducted after the podcasts. They were created to examine the strengths and weaknesses of this technique. Main elements in the questionnaire were the number of rehearsals, use of technological tools,

language elements used in podcasts, the level of satisfaction and motivation and willingness to repeat the experience. In a qualitative survey, a discussion about main challenges and areas of improvement were considered if students had to repeat the experience of podcasting.

RESULTS

Secondary data

“There are more than 7 billion mobile telephone subscriptions across the world, over 70% of which are in low- or middle- income countries.” Source: World Health Organisation (WHO) 2024.

65.36% users choose mobile phone over 33.92%, who opt for desktop usage, in Tunisia (statcounter.com. 2024)

fig.1: desktop vs mobile market share in Tunisia

(2024) source: statista.com

A questionnaire including four questions was published in google forms and shared with students on google classroom. 51 students responded. The results were as shown in the following tables.

Fig 2: Number of social media users in Tunisia as of 2023, by platform (million) source: statista.com

Quantitative survey

Would you like to repeat the experience of podcasting?

51 réponses

Number of rehearsals (repetitions)

50 réponses

Copier le graphiq

Technology used for podcasting

51 réponses

Copier le graphique

Which language element improved with podcasting?

51 réponses

Copier le graphique

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Secondary data analysis

Mobile phone applications are the most used tools compared to computers tools. This finding could be very insightful for future studies. Mobile phones are light, fast, cheap and even ecofriendly.

Furthermore, our findings highlight that, the use of mobile solutions, similar to social media content making, could be more motivating for students than computer tools. This stems from easiness and simplicity of usage, and mainly interactivity and availability of feedback options.

Mixed surveys results analysis

The results of the quantitative survey, the questionnaire, showed that pronunciation, accent and fluency were the most improved elements with podcasting compared to vocabulary and grammar. This element supports our hypothesis that podcasting can improve accent.

Mobile phone applications were the most used tools (extreme results) compared to computers and AI. This finding could be very insightful for future research, in terms of accessibility, awareness, and the relational side. Simply put, this finding highlights that, the use of mobile solutions similar to social media content making could be more motivating for students than AI solutions.

Furthermore, the number of rehearsals, a helpful element for improving pronunciation and accent through repetition and focus on articulation, showed that a considerable number of students repeated their voice recording in order to achieve the best desired results, thus, improving accent.

Extreme results proved the readiness of students to continue the experience of podcasting, thus proving the correlation between motivation and podcasting. Most students used background music to enhance the quality of the podcasts and that was a successful choice. They used creativity for varying the contents, for example creating their own radio programs, series and even making recorded interviews where they showed journalism skills.

Podcasts, whether in an audio or video form, make a highly communicative tool. In fact, according to Mehrabian 3V rule, voice makes up to 38% of communication while body language makes up for 55%, however, words account only for 7% of total communication. Not to mention the symbolic and suggestive power of pictures, background music, or videos embedded in podcasts.

Non-verbal elements		Audio version	Video version
Voice	Intonation		
	Stress		
	Volume		
	Pitch		
	Rate		
	Pauses/silence		
	Flow		
	Respiration/ flow		
Body language	Eye-contact		
	Posture		
	Appearance		
	Facial expressions		
	Hand gestures		

Table one: non-verbal elements in podcasts

Moreover, human voice used in podcasts is more 'relational', authentic and natural than AI generated voice, which is monotonous, dull and boring, despite advancement.

human voice	AI generated voice
emotional	most effective solutions
authentic	monotonous
expressive	dull
can carry mistakes in grammar, pronunciation,	depends on input
inconsistency in rate volume	consistent
silence and hesitation	boring
intonation (showing emotions)	'dead' sound
personalised	
diversely	

Table two: Human voice versus AI generated voice

Podcasts are of high value in terms of potential for accent improvement. They would be more motivating especially with a combination of CALL (text-to-speech), rehearsal, background music, images or video.

Finally, the experience of podcasting proves a high correlation with building a positive self image. A positive self image is translated in a higher self-confidence, esteem, awareness, love, and empathy for oneself. A connection with the self. BAŞARAN (2014)

Another element that is polished through podcasts is creativity, with the freedom of content making management, that is content, setting, theme and sound and visual effects.

CONCLUSION

Mobile phone technology has replaced paper based education. Smartphones are widely used in language learning classes. This technology can provide a valuable way for education if well used. Teachers can turn social media tools mainly podcasting into a learning opportunity to improve linguistic competence mainly podcasting. Our research has positively confirmed the hypothesis that podcasting can improve accent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results found in this paper, some recommendations have been made

- Mobile technology is a gold mine in second language education, instructors should be willing to explore possible uses of this technology, and explore the challenges accompanied with it Ducate, L. and Lomicka, L. (2009).
- Podcasts can be used to improve autonomy, linguistic competence, communication, motivation and character.
- AI application is limited and remains less relational, Warschauer, M, & Xu, Y. (2024) this stems from lack of awareness among the educational stakeholders.
- The likely dangers of podcasting include lack of cybersecurity awareness; privacy rules and copyrights must be taken into account.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kopnina, H. (2020). Education for the future? Critical evaluation of education for sustainable development goals. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 51(4), 280–291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2019.1710444>

- [2] Gulbarshyn, Belgibayeva., Aknur, S., Baimakhan., Zhanna, M, Akparova. (2024). The Formation of English Language Communicative Competence through Podcasts. A. Âsauı atyndağy Halykaralyq qazaq-turik universitetinın habarşysy, 132(2):232-242. doi: 10.47526/2024-2/2664-0686.57
- [3] Charif, Ben-boulaid. (2013). Using podcasts in teaching oral expression to help improve students' fluency in English an innovative approach that complies with lmd requirement in departments of english in Algeria. 29(1):107-120.
- [4] Kilickaya, F. (2006). 'Text-To-Speech Technology': What Does It Offer To Foreign Language Learners?. *CALL-EJ Online*, 7(2), 7-2.
- [5] Sven, L., Mattys, Alan, D., Baddeley. (2019). Working Memory And Second Language Accent Acquisition. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 33(6) :1113-1123. [https://doi :10.1002/ACP.3554](https://doi.org/10.1002/ACP.3554)
- [6] Leticia, González, Pérez. (2018). Student-created vodcast based on tv series in tefl in secondary education.
- [7] Indahsari, D. (2020). Using podcast for EFL students in language learning. *JEES (Journal of English Educators Society)*, 5(2), 103-108. <https://doi.org/10.21070/jees.v5i2.767>
- [8] Ducate, L. and Lomicka, L. (2009). Podcasting: An effective tool for honing language students' pronunciation? *Language Learning & Technology* 13, 66–86.
- [9] Sehan, Zainurrahman, Beware of the Disadvantages of Computer-Assisted Language Learning:A Thematic Analysis of Existing Literature (June 7, 2023).
- [10] Warschauer, M, & Xu, Y. (2024). Generative AI for language learning: Entering a new era. *Language Learning & Technology*, 28(2), 1–4. <https://hdl.handle.net/10125/73569>
- [11] Tutku başöz, Pre-service EFL Teachers Attitudes towards Language Learning through Social Media Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 232:430-438. October 2016 (October 2016) Tutku Başöz,
- [12] Chen, C.F. (2007). Computer-assisted language learning and teaching. Retrieved, May 20, 2009, from <http://www.nkfust.edu.tw/~emchen/CALL/>.
- [13] Haryadi, S. H. (2020). Integrating "English Pronunciation" App Into Pronunciation Teaching: How It Affects Students' Participation and Learning. *Participation and Learning*
- [14] Hung, T. M. (2015). The impact of using smartphone apps on learners' pronunciation accuracy. *English Language Teaching*, 8(8), 1-8.
- [15] Kim, N. Y., Cha, Y., & Kim, H.- S. (2019). Future English learning: Chatbots and artificial intelligence. *Multimedia Assisted Language Learning*, 22(3), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.15702/mall.2019.22.3.32>
- [16] Levy, M. (2016). *CALL dimensions: Options and issues in computer-assisted language learning*. Routledge.
- [17] Yang, H., Kim, H., Lee, J., & Shin, D. (2022). Implementation of an AI chatbot as an English conversation partner in EFL speaking classes. *ReCALL FirstView*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344022000039>
- [18] Phillips, Birgit. Student-Produced Podcasts in Language Learning--Exploring Student Perceptions of Podcast Activities. *IAFOR Jurnal of Education*, v5 n3 p157-171 Win 2017
- [19] Süleyman BAŞARAN1 & Neşe CABAROĞLU2. THE EFFECT OF LANGUAGE LEARNING PODCASTS ON ENGLISH SELF-EFFICACY *International Journal of Language Academy* Volume 2/2 Summer 2014 p. 48/69

APPENDICES

Secondary data

<https://www.who.int/activities/Addressing-mobile-health>

<https://gs.statcounter.com/platform-market-share/desktop-mobile-tablet/tunisia/2022>

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1284841/number-of-social-media-users-in-tunisia-by-platform/>